

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.5.4: Urbanization and pollution

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Description

Section 3.5.4 assesses the interaction between urbanisation and pollution as a driver for the introduction of invasive alien species in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on these drivers and possible reports of their interaction. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5:

Search 6:

Search 7:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: Urban* AND pollution AND invas*

Search 2: Urbanisation AND Pollution

Search 3: Urbanization AND Pollution

Search 4: Urban* AND pollution AND driver AND invasi*

Search 5: Urban* AND pollution AND introduction AND invasi*

Search 6: Urban* AND pollution AND spread AND invasi*

Search 7: Urban* AND noise pollution AND spread AND invasi*

- **Search engine:** Web of Science

-**Searched time period:**

Search 1-7: 1900 to 2021

- **Date:**

Search 1: 5 August 2021

Search 2 &3: 11 August 2021

Search 4: 25 August 2021

Search 5-7: 26 August 2021

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

Search 1: 33 (1 paper selected for review)

Search 2: 6 (4 paper selected for review)

Search 3: 40 (3 paper selected for review)

Search 4: 15 (0 papers selected for review)

Search 5: 23 (2 papers selected for review)

Search 6: 32 (2 papers selected for review)

Search 7: 2 (0 papers selected for review)

Selection criteria:

Articles that specified the interaction between urbanisation and pollution as a vector of introduction of invasive alien species.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 7

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: From the initial 151 papers found, the first scan included reviewing from the title and abstracts which ones were the most representative for the section, the ones that could include information of the interaction between urbanisation and pollution as a vector of introduction for

IAS were fully read, and then 12 were selected to draft the section. Diversity on ecosystems and stages of the invasive process was prioritised.

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)